

RAPID MICROPROPAGATION OF NODAL EXPLANT OF *Eclipta alba* (L.); AN ENDANGERED, MEDICINALLY IMPORTANT PLANT¹Gawali R. R., ²Wagh D. S., ¹Kharade S. S., ²Gaddekar P. S., ¹Kokare N. D., ¹Nandre R. S.,¹Department of Plant Biotechnology, K. K. Wagh College of Agricultural Biotechnology, Nashik- 422003, India.²Department of Microbial & Environmental Biotechnology, K. K. Wagh College of Agricultural Biotechnology, Nashik-422003, India.*Corresponding author: Email: ds.wagh@kkwagh.edu.in, hrutujagawali@gmail.com

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Abstract

The study was undertaken with a view to standardized a protocol for rapid micropropagation of *Eclipta alba* (L.). Single nodal segment (NS) was used as an explant. The present study was conducted at Plant Tissue Culture Laboratory of K. K. Wagh College of Agricultural Biotechnology, Nashik, during the year 2022-2023.

In present study, explants were sterilized with different sterilizing agents such as Bavistin (0.2%), HgCl₂ (0.01%) and 70% ethanol. Sterilized explants were cultured on Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium supplemented with different concentrations of plant growth hormones for shoot initiation BAP alone (0.0, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0 mg/L), multiplication BAP (0.0, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0 mg/L) and NAA (0.1 mg/L) and rooting IBA (0.0, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5 mg/L). Primary and secondary hardening was done in potting mixture containing autoclaved black soil: vermicompost: cocopeat (1:1:1) and garden black soil, cocopeat and red soil (1:1:1) respectively.

In present investigation 0.2% Bavistin (fungicide) showed maximum respond to prevent fungal contamination. Highest shoot initiation (100%) was observed on a MS medium fortified with BAP (1.0 mg/L). Maximum shoot multiplication on a MS medium supplemented with BAP (1.0 mg/L) + NAA (0.1 mg/L). Maximum root initiation was observed on half strength MS medium supplemented with IBA (0.5 mg/L). In vitro regenerated plantlets hardened on the mixture of autoclaved black soil: vermicompost: cocopeat (1:1:1). After 14 weeks in vitro plantlets transferred in green house for acclimatization where, 85% survival rate was recorded.

Regeneration protocol was successfully standardized. Therefore, it can be used for large scale propagation of disease free, high yielding and quality of plant and in vitro propagation helps to rapid multiplication of endangered species and medicinal plant. Bhringraj has massive demand in Ayurvedic medicine and pharmaceutical industry.

Keywords: Bhringraj, Nodal explant, In vitro.

Introduction

Eclipta alba (L.) Hassk. is a small branched herb with white flower heads belonging to the family Asteraceae [16]. *Eclipta alba* (L.) is one of most well-known and valuable medicinal plants in India. It is commonly named as false daisy and Bhringaraj and Karisilakanni. Genus *Eclipta* originated from the Greek word "Deficient" which means absence of the bristles and awns on the fruits [6]. *Eclipta alba* (L.) Hassk (Asteraceae) commonly known as False Daisy [14]. *Eclipta alba* (L.) distributed in tropical and sub-tropical region of the word [2].

This medicinal plant has rich ethnomedicinal history. *E. alba* and its therapeutic value has also been mentioned in classical text "Bhavaprakash". In Ayurveda, it is named as "bhringoraja", in Unani system; it is named as "bhangra" whereas in Siddha it is named as "karissalaankanni". *E. alba* is categorized into three categories on the basis of the color of the flowers/fruits which are white-flowering, the yellow-flowering, and the black-fruited. Each type is found in marshes, rivers, and lakes or on the foothills of the Himalayas in India. This medicinal plant is mostly used in tropical and sub-tropical regions as a traditional medicine. It is also utilized as a functional food [6]. *E. alba* is one of such medicinally important herb that possesses different significant properties. This is used as dyeing agent for hair blackening and also prevents premature hair-fall [10].

India, one among the largest producers of medicinal herbs and appropriately called the botanical garden of the world, is in the 10th position of the world's plant diversity wealth, which is distributed across 16 agro-climatic zones. Today, medicinal plants are important to the global economy, as approximately 80% of traditional medicine preparations involve the use of plants or plant extracts. The increasing demand for herbal medicines in recent years due to their fewer side effects in comparison to synthetic drugs and antibiotics has highlighted the need for conservation and propagation of medicinal plants. In India, about 1,000 plants have been used in the traditional systems of medicine, while tribals use more than 7,500 plant species for medicinal purposes. The major concern is that most of the medicinal plants are collected from the wild populations, and over 70% of the plant collection involves destructive harvesting mainly

because of the use of plant parts like leaf, bark, wood and whole plants. [14].

Eclipta alba (L.) Hassk. contains wide range of active principles which include coumestans, alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, polyacetylenes, tri-terpenoids. The leaves, roots & areal parts are reported to contain a wide range of active principles having medicinal values. The polypeptide isolated from this plant yield cystine, glutamic acid, phenyl alanine, tyrosine & methionine on hydrolysis. Nicotine and nicotinic acid are reported to occur in this plant. The fresh juice of leaves is used for increasing appetite, improving digestion and as a mild bowel regulator [16].

The alcoholic extract of the plant has shown antiviral activity against Ranikhet disease virus. *Eclipta alba* is widely used in India as a cholagogue and deobstruent in hepatic enlargement, for jaundice and other ailments of the liver and gall bladder. The roots have emetic and purgative properties and it is applied externally as an antiseptic to ulcer and wounds in cattle. The shoot extract shows anti microbial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* [14]. The plant extracts have been reported to enclose quite a lot of phytoconstituents such as wedelolactone, dimethyl-wedelolactone, eclalbatin, oleanolic acid, ursolic acid, stigmasterol-3-Oglucoside, ecliptasaponin, etc. The plant involves many other biological activities like hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, antiviral, antibacterial, hypotensive, spasmogenic, antioxidant, analgesic, cardioprotective and antianaphylactic properties [10].

In vitro culture techniques offer a viable tool for bulk multiplication of genetically identical plant material, large scale production and germplasm conservation of valuable plants. The in vitro technology could be a cost effective means of high-volume production of the elite planting material throughout the year, without any seasonal constraints. Hence, the study was aimed to establish a rapid and reproducible in vitro regeneration system for *E. alba* using nodal explants on modified B5 medium [9]. The plant is conventionally propagated through seeds and grows generally in moist and wet places. Due to this habit, it is vulnerable to pests and diseases. In order to avoid using contaminated pharmaceutical raw materials, it is necessary to develop an alternative source of propagation and transport of healthy plants. The present study was therefore

undertaken to develop a protocol for rapid micropropagation of this important medicinal herb through in vitro culture [13].

Material and Methods

Explant collection and surface sterilization

The present study was carried out at plant tissue culture laboratory of K. K. Wagh College of Agricultural Biotechnology, Nashik-422003, during the year 2022-2023. Nodal segment were collected from disease free healthy Bhringraj plant from Nashik district of Maharashtra state and the collected Nodal segment were washed with running tap water to remove adhering soil. The scally leaves and roots removes carefully and Node 1-2 cm in length were trimmed about 4-5 cm in length Surface sterilized of trimmed nodal were done with 0.2% (w/v) Bavistin (fungicide) solution for 10 minutes. Explants were treated with 0.01% mercuric chloride for 4 minute and 70% ethanol for 30 seconds. The explants were washed with 3-4 times with sterile distilled water to remove the traces of sterilants (Plate 1).

Culture condition and shoot initiation

The sterilized explants were inoculated on MS (Murashige and Skoog's, 1962) medium containing different concentrations of BAP (Control-3mg/l) with 3% sucrose and 8 g/L agar. The inoculated culture bottles were kept in culture room at the temperature 25 ± 2 °C, relative humidity of 75-80%, 16/8 hr photoperiod and light intensity 1000-2000 lux for the growth of explant. The experiment was carried out in 6 replication with 1 explant for each treatment. Observations were recorded the shoot developed from shoot initiation medium were transferred on shoot multiplication medium containing same concentration of BAP (control-3.0 mg/L) with NAA (0.1 mg/L) for 3-4 week. The experiment for each treatment was replicated 6 times.

Root induction and hardening

Well-developed shoots were excised and inoculated on a half strength MS media fortified with (control-1.5 mg/L). Rooted plantlets were successfully transferred to plastic pots containing autoclaved black soil, vermicompost and cocopeat (1:1:1) for primary hardening of 4 weeks. After 4 weeks primary hardened well developed plantlets transferred to large size pots containing garden black soil, cocopeat and red soil (1:1:1) for 50-60 days.

Table 2. Effect of BAP and NAA on shoot Multiplication

Treatment code	PGR's concentration (mg/L)	No. of Explant inoculated	Shoot Multiplication	Shoot multiplication %
T0	Control	6	0	0
T1	BAP (0.5 mg/L)	6	4	66.67
T2	BAP (1.0 mg/L)	6	6	100
T3	BAP (1.5 mg/L)	6	4	66.67
T4	BAP (2.0 mg/L)	6	3	50
T5	BAP (2.5 mg/L)	6	3	50
T6	BAP (3.0 mg/L)	6	2	3.33

In vitro rooting

Root initiation was observed 4 weeks within the transfer of elongated shoots onto the half strength MS medium containing IBA (0.0-1.5 mg/L). In the present study early rooting was observed when the MS

Table 3. Effect of IBA on root regeneration from regenerated shoots of Bhringraj

Treatment code	PGR's concentration (mg/L)	Root observation	No. of roots/ plant	Root length (cm)
T1	½ MS+ IBA (0.0 mg/L)	Observed	0	0
T2	½ MS + IBA (0.5 mg/L)	Observed	3	2.5
T3	½ MS + IBA (1.0 mg/L)	observed	9	7.2
T4	½ MS + IBA (1.5 mg/L)	observed	4	4.8

Hardening and acclimatization

Elongated and rooted plantlets were taken out from culture vessels and roots were carefully washed thoroughly with tap water to remove the Agar. *In vitro* regenerated roots treated with 0.1% (w/v) Bavistin for 2-3 minutes and washed with tap water and successfully transferred to plastic pot containing autoclaved black soil, vermicompost and cocopeat (1:1:1) and potting substrates were moistened with tap water where, 100% survivability of primary

Data collection and analysis

Five observations viz., Number of days required for shoot initiation, shoot induction percentage, shoot length, root length and number of roots were recorded after specific interval of time.

Results and Discussion

Culture establishment

In the present investigation, explants were inoculated on MS basal medium alone and MS medium supplemented with different types and concentration of BAP either alone or in combination with IBA (Table 1, plate 2). The observation shows the establishment of culture on MS media with various concentrations of growth hormones. It was observed that the minimum time was required by the MS medium fortified with BAP (0.0 mg/L). The 100% shoot induction percentage was observed on MS media supplemented with BAP (1.0 mg/L).

Table 1. Effect of cytokinin concentrations on shoot initiation from shoot tip explant

Treatment code	Concentrations of PGR's (mg/L)	No. of explants inoculated	No. of explants responded	Shoot induction (%)
T0	MS (Control)	6	0	0
T1	MS + BAP 0.5	6	3	50
T2	MS + BAP 1.0	6	6	100
T3	MS + BAP 1.5	6	4	66.67
T5	MS + BAP 2.0	6	3	50
T6	MS + BAP 2.5	6	2	33.3
T7	MS + BAP 3.0	6	3	50

Shoot Multiplication

After the initiation the shoots were transferred into another media bottles with different concentration of BAP and NAA to find out in which concentration the rate was higher. Highest shoot multiplication formation was observed in the bottle containing (1 mg/l) BAP with (0.1mg/l) NAA. The multiplication stage was completed within 25-30 days. The lowest number of shoots was seen in control.

basal medium supplemented with IBA. The maximum root length (8.5 cm) and 6-7 roots per shoot were observed on half strength MS medium supplemented with IBA (0.5 mg/L) after 2 weeks which was shown in plate no 3.

hardened plantlets showed. After 40 days Bhringraj plantlets transferred for secondary hardening in large size pots containing garden black soil, cocopeat and red soil (1:1:1). After 14 weeks *in vitro* plantlets transferred in green house for acclimatization where, 80% survival rate was recorded.

Conclusion

The present study concluded that 0.2% Bavistin (fungicide) showed maximum respond to prevent fungal contamination. MS medium

supplemented with BAP 1.0 mg/L showed highest response for shoot initiation. 8 to 9 leaves and multiplied shoots about 11.2 cm were observed on MS medium supplemented with BAP (1.0 mg/L) + NAA (0.1 mg/L). Half strength MS medium supplemented with IBA (0.5 mg/L) showed maximum response for the rooting. During primary hardening 100% survivability observed whereas, 80% response of secondary plantlets was observed. Therefore, *in vitro* regeneration of Bhringraj with various concentration of plant growth hormones can be used it can for large scale propagation of disease free, high yielding and quality of plant and *in vitro* propagation helps to rapid multiplication of endangered Species and medicinal plant. Bhringraj has massive demand in Ayurvedic medicine and pharmaceutical industry.

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Consent

All the authors gave explicit consent to submit and that they obtained consent from the responsible authorities at the institute. It has not been submitted simultaneously for publication in any other journal.

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A)

B)

C)

D)

Plate 1. Sterilization of explants (Nodal segment) with different sterilizing agents

A) Nodal segment (explant)

B) Treatment of explants with 0.2% Bavistin solution

C) Treatment of explants with 0.01% Mercuric Chloride solution

D) Treatment of explants with 70% Ethanol.

Plate 2. *In vitro* establishment of explant

A) Culture initiation

B) Greening of culture

C) Shoot induction on MS medium containing BAP (1.5, 2.0, 4.0, 6.0 mg/L) and BAP (3.0 mg/L) and IAA/ IBA (2.0 mg/L)

D) Shoot Multiplication on MS medium supplemented with BAP (3.0 mg/L) and NAA (1.0, 1.5, 2.0 mg/L)

A)

B)

C)

Plate 3. *In vitro* establishment of explantA) *In vitro* rooting on half strength MS medium fortified with IAA (1.0, 1.5 mg/L) and IBA (1.0, 1.5 mg/L)

B) Primary hardened plantlets

C) Secondary hardened plantlets